

March 2021: Top Read Articles in VLSI design & Communication Systems

**International Journal of VLSI design &
Communication Systems (VLSICS)**

ISSN: 0976 - 1357 (Online); 0976 - 1527(print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vlsics.html>

VERIFICATION OF DRIVER LOGIC USING AMBA AXI UVM

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ABSTRACT

Advanced Extensible Interface (AXI) is the most commonly used bus protocols in the day-to-day because of its high performance and high-frequency operation without using complex bridges. AXI is also backwardcompatible with existing AHB and APB interfaces. So verification of driver logic using AMBA-AXI UVM is presented in this paper. The AXI is used for multiple outstanding operations which is only possible in the other protocol but it is possible in AXI because it contains different write address and data channels and AXI also supports out of order transfer based on the transaction ID which is generated at the start of the transfer. The driver logic for the AXI has been designed and implemented using the Universal Verification Methodology (UVM).The signaling of the five channels such as write address, write data, write response, read address, read data channel of AXI protocol are considered for verification. According to the AXI protocol,the signals of these channels are driven to the interconnect and results are observed for single master and single slave. The driver logic has been implemented and verified successfully according to AXI protocol using the Rivera Pro. The results observed for single master and single slave have shown the correctness of AMBA-AXI design in Verilog.

KEYWORDS

AMBA(Advance Microcontroller Bus Architecture),AXI(Advanced Extensible Interface),UVM(Universal Verification Methodology),channel.

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol9.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Amba axi protocol specification, arm, 2011.
- [2] Gayathri m, rini sebastian, silpa rose mary, anoop thomas, “a sv-uvm framework verification of sgmiip core with reusable axi to wb bridge uvc”, ieeep,3rd international on advance computing and communication systems,jan 22 & 23 ,2016 ,coimbatore, india.
- [3] Rini sebastian, silpa rose mary, gayathri m, anoop thomas, “assertion based verification of sgmiip core incorporating axi transaction verification model”, ieeep,international conference on control, communication & computing india (iccc), 19-21 november 2015 , trivandrum.
- [4] Golla mahesh, sakthivel.s.m, verification ip for an amba-axi protocol using system verilog, international journal ofengineering research and general science, volume 3, issue 1, januaryfebruary, 2015.
- [5] Mahendra.b.m,ramachandra.a.c, bus functional model verification ip development of axi protocol, international journal ofengineeringresearch andgeneral science, volume 3, special issue 1, february, 2014
- [6] Anusharanga, l. harivenkatesh, venkanna, design and implementation of amba-axi protocol using vhdl for soc integration, international journal of engineering research and general science, vol. 2, issue4, july-august 20,2012.

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VLSI DESIGN OF AMBA BASED AHB2APB BRIDGE

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ABSTRACT

The Advanced Microcontroller Bus Architecture (AMBA) is an open System-on-Chip bus protocol for highperformance buses to communicate with low-power devices. In the AMBA Advanced High Performance bus (AHB) a system bus is used to connect a processor, a DSP, and high-performance memory controllers where as the AMBA Advanced Peripheral Bus (APB) is used to connect (Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter) UART. It also contains a Bridge, which connects the AHB and APB buses. Bridges are standard bus-to-bus interfaces that allow IPs connected to different buses to communicate with each other in a standardized way. So AHB2APB bridge is designed, implemented using VERILOG tool and tested using Verilog testbench and is reported in this paper. A synthesizable RTL code of a complex interface bridge between AHB and APB is developed and known as AHB2APB Bridge. The simulated AHB2APB Bridge results are promising and can be further tested for its verstality by writing a verification program using UVM in future.

KEYWORDS

AMBA; AHB2APB; SOC; VERILOG; XILINX

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol9.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Jaehoon Song, Student member, IEEE et al.,” An Efficient SOC Test Technique by Reusing On/OffChip Bus Bridge”. IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems-I: Regular Papers, Vol. 56, No.3, March 2009.
- [2] Krishna Sekar, Member, IEEE et al.” Dynamically Configurable Bus Topologies for HighPerformance On-Chip Communication”. IEEE transactions on very large-scale integration (Vlsi) systems, vol. 16, no. 10, October 2008.
- [3] G. Geetha Reddy et al.,” Implementation of bus bridge between AHB and OCP”. Global Journal of Advanced Engineering Technologies, Vol 1, Issue4-2012 ISSN: 2277-6370.
- [4] Kalluri Usha and T. Ashok Kumar,” AXI To Apb Interface Design Using Verilog”. IOSR Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering, p- ISSN: 2278-8735. Volume 8, Issue 5 (Nov. - Dec. 2013), pg. 01-09.
- [5] Vani.R.M and Merope,” Design of AMBA based AHB2APB bridge” IJCSNS international journal of computer science and network security, vol.10, no.11, November 2010
- [6] Priyanka M Shettar¹, Ashwin Kumar “Verification IP of AMBA AXI V1.0 Using UVM”. IOSR Journal of VLSI and Signal Processing (IOSR-JVSP) Volume 6, Issue 3, Ver. II (May -Jun. 2016), pg. 54-58.

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EXTENDED K-MAP FOR MINIMIZING MULTIPLE OUTPUT LOGIC CIRCUITS

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ABSTRACT

Minimization of multiple output functions of a digital logic circuit is a classic research problem. Minimal circuit is obtained by using multiple Karnaugh Maps (K-map), one for each function. In this paper we propose a novel technique that uses a single Karnaugh Map for minimizing multiple outputs of a single circuit. The algorithm basically accumulates multiple K-Maps into a single K-Map. Finding minimal numbers of minterms are easier using our proposed clustering technique. Experimental results show that minimization of digital circuits where more than one output functions are involved, our extended K-Map approach is more efficient as compare to multiple K-Map approach.

KEYWORDS

Boolean Algebra, Karnaugh Map, Digital Logic Circuit, Clustering.

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol4.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Boole G. (1954): *An Investigation of the Laws of Thought*. — New York: Dover Publications.
- [2] Shannon C.E. (1938): A symbolic analysis of relay and switching circuits. —*Trans. AIEE*, Vol. 57, No. 6, pp. 713–723.
- [3] Karnaugh M. (1953): The map method for synthesis of combinatorial logic circuits. — *Trans. AIEE Comm. Electron.*, Vol. 72, No. 4, pp. 593–598.
- [4] McCluskey E. J. (1956), “Minimization of Boolean functions”, *Bell System Tech. J.*, Vol. 35, No. 5, pp. 1417–1444.
- [5] Quine W. V. (1952), “The problem of simplifying truth tables”, *Amer. Math. Month.*, Vol. 59, No. 8, pp. 521–531.
- [6] Petrick S. K. (1959), “On the minimization of Boolean functions”, *Proc. Int. Conf. Information Processing*, Paris: Unesco, pp. 422–423.
- [7] McCluskey E. J. (1965), “Introduction to the Theory of Switching Circuits”, New York, McGrawHill.
- [8] Biswas N. N. (1971), “Minimization of Boolean Functions”, *IEEE Trans. on Computers*, Vol. C-20, pp. 925-929.
- [9] Hong S. J., Cain R. G., Ostapko D. L. (1974), “MINI: A Heuristic Approach for Logic Minimization”, *IBM Journal of Research and Development*, Vol. 18, pp. 443-458.
- [10] Rhyne V. T., Noe P. S., McKinney M. H., and Pooch U.W. (1977) “A New Technique for the Fast Minimization of Switching Functions”, *IEEE Trans. on Computers*, Vol. C-26, pp. 757-764.

MULTISIM DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF 2.2GHz LNA FOR WIRELESS COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the work done on the design and simulation of a high frequency low noise amplifier for wireless communication. The purpose of the amplifier is to amplify the received RF path of a wireless network. With high gain, high sensitivity and low noise using Bipolar Junction transistor (BJT). The design methodology requires analysis of the transistor for stability, proper matching, network selection and fabrication. The BJT transistor was chosen for the design of the LNA due to its low noise and good gain at high frequency. These properties were confirmed using some measurement techniques including Network Analyzer, frequency analyzer Probe and Oscilloscope for the simulation and practical testing of the amplifier to verify the performance of the designed High frequency Low noise amplifier. The design goals of noise figure of 0.52dB-0.7dB and bias conditions are $V_{cc} = 3.5$ V and $I_{cc} = 55$ mA to produce 16.8 dB gain across the 0.4–2.2GHz band.

KEYWORDS

Amplifier, Bipolar Junction Transistor, Stability, LNA, Fabrication, Multism

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<http://aircse.org/journal/vlsi/vol5.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Dixit, N.: Design And Performance Of Low Voltage, Low Noise 900MHz Amplifier, No. 43-51, Pp. 26,2006
- [2] A.O. Fadamirol and E.O. Ogunti Design of a High Frequency and High Sensitive Low Noise Amplifier Asian Journal of Engineering and Technology (ISSN: 2321 – 2462) Volume 01– Issue 02, June 2013
- [3] Yu Lin Wei and Jun De Jin, “A low power low noise amplifier for K-band applications,” IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 116-118, Feb. 2009
- [4] Bonghyuk Park, Sangsungs Choi, and Songcheol Hong, “A low noise amplifier with tunable interference rejection for 3.1 to 10.6 GHz UWB systems,” IEEE Microwave and Wireless Components Letters, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 40-42, Jan 2010.
- [5] Mercer, S.: An Introduction to Low-Noise Amplifier Design, RF Design, Pp.4 2008
- [6] Viranjay M. Srivastava, K. S. Yadav, and G. Singh, “Design and performance analysis of cylindrical surrounding double-gate MOSFET for RF switch,” Microelectronics Journal, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 1124-1135, Oct. 2011
- [7] Shouxian, M.: Dival Band Low Noise Amplifier Design For Bluetooth And Hiper Law Application. PhD Dissertation In Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Nanyang Technological University.2006
- [8] H. W. Chiu, “A 2.17 dB NF 5 GHz band monolithic CMOS LNA with 10 mW DC power consumption,” IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Tech., vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 813-824, March 2005.
- [9] Aniket, P.J., Mahaya, S.P., Joshi, B.C.s, Design and Development of Low Noise Amplifier for RF/MW Receiver. Journal of Scientific Research, Vol.2 Issue 6.2013

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF CAR PARKING SYSTEM ON FPGA

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ABSTRACT

As, the number of vehicles are increased day by day in rapid manner. It causes the problem of traffic congestion, pollution (noise and air). To overcome this problem A FPGA based parking system has been proposed. In this paper, parking system is implemented using Finite State Machine modelling. The system has two main modules i.e. identification module and slot checking module. Identification module identifies the visitor. Slot checking module checks the slot status. These modules are modelled in HDL and implemented on FPGA. A prototype of parking system is designed with various interfaces like sensor interfacing, stepper motor and LCD.

KEYWORDS

Finite State Machine; Parking System; Virtex- 5;

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol4.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Du Shaobo; Sun Shibao;,(2012) "The research and design of intellectual parking system based on RFID," Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD), 2012 9th International Conference on, pp.2427-2430.
- [2] Gongjun Yan; Weiming Yang; Rawat, D.B.; Olariu, S.,(2011) "SmartParking: A Secure and Intelligent Parking System," Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine, IEEE , vol.3, no.1, pp.18-30.
- [3] Liu Liang; Zhang Lei; Xiao Jin; ,(2011) "The simulation of an auto-parking system," Industrial Electronics and Applications (ICIEA), 2011 6th IEEE Conference on , pp.249-253.
- [4] Soh Chun Khang; Teoh Jie Hong; Tan Saw Chin; Shengqiong Wang;(2010) , "Wireless MobileBased Shopping Mall Car Parking System (WMCPS)," Services Computing Conference (APSCC), 2010 IEEE Asia-Pacific , pp.573-577.
- [5] Gupta, A.; Divekar, R.; Agrawal, M.; ,(2010) "Autonomous parallel parking system for Ackerman steering four wheelers," Computational Intelligence and Computing Research (ICCIC), 2010 IEEE International Conference on , pp.1-6.
- [6] Hua-Chun Tan; Jie Zhang; Xin-Chen Ye; Hui-Ze Li; Pei Zhu; Qing-Hua Zhao;(2009) , "Intelligent car-searching system for large park," Machine Learning and Cybernetics, 2009 International Conference on , vol.6, no., pp.3134-3138.
- [7] Srikanth, S.V.; Pramod, P.J.; Dileep, K.P.; Tapas, S.; Patil, M.U.; Sarat, C.B.N.:(2009) , "Design and Implementation of a Prototype Smart PARKing (SPARK) System Using Wireless Sensor Networks," Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops, 2009. WAINA '09. International Conference on , pp.401-406.
- [8] Gongjun Yan; Olariu, S.; Weigle, M.C.; Abuelela, M.; ,(2008) "SmartParking: A Secure and Intelligent Parking System Using NOTICE," Intelligent Transportation Systems, 2008. ITSC 2008. 11th International IEEE Conference on , pp.569-574.
- [9] Tsung-hua Hsu; Jing-Fu Liu; Pen-Ning Yu; Wang-Shuan Lee; Jia-Sing Hsu; ,(2008) "Development of an automatic parking system for vehicle," Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference, 2008. VPPC '08. IEEE , pp.1-6.
- [10] Insop Song; Gowan, K.; Nery, J.; Han, H.; Sheng, T.; Li, H.; Karray, F.; ,(2006) "Intelligent Parking System Design Using FPGA," Field Programmable Logic and Applications, 2006. FPL '06. International Conference on , pp.1-6.
- [11] http://www.ops.fhwa.dot.gov/congestion_report/chapter3.htm#footer14

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EVALUATION OF ATM FUNCTIONING USING VHDL AND FPGA

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ABSTRACT

It has been almost four decades that banks and other financial organizations have been gradually computerised, in order to improve service and efficiency and to reduce cost. The birth of Electronic Fund Transfer and Automated Teller Machines has given rise to 24-hour banking and a greater variety of services for the customer. This method uses a computer to transfer debits and credits, with the help of electronic pulses, which are carried through wires either to a magnetic disk or tape. ATM (Automated Teller Machine) has become an important part in our daily lives. People use ATM for various purposes such as money withdrawal, checking balance, changing password etc. Since it mainly deals with people's money, it has to be a secure system on which we can rely. We have taken a step towards increasing this security and integrity by trying to implement the functioning of an ATM using VLSI-based programming, HDL(Hardware Description Language).The conventional coding languages such as C,C++ are replaced by VHDL(Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language) so that the code cannot be easily hacked or changed. This article consists of an insight into the various functions that can be performed using an ATM, a brief description of the Coding and the obtained simulation results. It also consists of the implementation of the code using FPGA Kit (Spartan3; Model no.-XC 3S50).

KEYWORDS

ATM (Automated Teller Machine), Security, HDL (Hardware Description Language), FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array).

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<http://aircse.org/journal/vlsi/vol6.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Yingxu Wang and Yanan Zhang, "The Formal Design Model of an Automatic Teller Machine (ATM)" University of Calgary, Canada, International Journal of Software Science and Computational Intelligence, 2(1), 102-131, January-March 2010.
- [2] Avenet Avenue, user's guide, Xilinx® Spartan™-3 Development Kit.
- [3] Stanley MAZOR and Patricia LINGSTRAAT, "A guide to VHDL (2nd Edition)", copyright 1993, Kluwer Academic Publishers, pp no: 1-1 to 7-16.
- [4] http://www.fpga.com.cn/hdl/training/Vhdl_Golden_Reference_Guide.pdf
- [5] Peter J. Ashenden and Jim Lewis, "The Designer's Guide to VHDL (3rd Edition)" copyright 2008, Morgan Kaufmann Publication, pp no:207-225.
- [6] Pong P. Chu "RTL Hardware Design Using VHDL, Coding For Efficiency, portability and Scalability", Wiley Interscience a John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Publication, pp no:23-160.
- [7] Hardware Implementation of Watchdog Timer for Application in ATM Machine Using Verilog and FPGA Iqbalur Rahman Rokon, Toufiq Rahman, Md. Murtoza Ali Quader, and Mukit Alam, International Conference on Electronics, Biomedical Engineering and its Applications (ICEBEA'2012) Jan. 7-8, 2012 Dubai

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DESIGN OF HIGH EFFICIENCY TWO STAGE POWER AMPLIFIER IN 0.13UM RF CMOS TECHNOLOGY FOR 2.4 GHZ WLAN APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

A two stage CMOS power amplifier is implemented in 0.13 μ m RF CMOS technology using ADS tool operating at 2.4 GHz with dc supply of 2.5 V. Driver stage as the input stage and power stage as the output stage are the two stages. A cascode topology is used in the driver stage and basic topology is used in the power stage. Output power at 1dB compression point is 20.028 dBm and maximum output power delivered by this circuit is 22.002 dBm. Power added efficiency calculated at 1 dB compression point is 44.669 % whereas the maximum power added efficiency comes out to be 70.196 %. The input return and output return losses are -11.132 dB and -12.467 dB respectively. Isolation loss and small signal gain are calculated to be -61.889 dB and 43.745 dB respectively. This circuit shows power gain of 42.728 dB at 1dB compression point. The total dc current flowing through this circuit is 0.0901 A. MOSFET only bias circuits are used to reduce total dc current. This circuit is designed for application in WLAN.

KEYWORDS

RFIC, RF CMOS, PAE, Impedance Matching, Cascode Topology

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol1.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] M.Hella, M.Ismail, "RF CMOS Power Amplifiers: Theory, Design and Implementation", Ohio State University
- [2] Thomas H. Lee, "The Design of CMOS Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits", Second Edition, Cambridge University Press
- [3] Ho Ka Wai, "A 1-V CMOS Power Amplifier for Bluetooth Applications", Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, 2002
- [4] Kyu Hwan An, "CMOS RF POWER AMPLIFIERS FOR MOBILE WIRELESS COMMUNICATIONS", Georgia Institute of Technology, 2009
- [5] Ravinder Kumar, Munish Kumar, Balraj, "Design and Implementation of a High Efficiency CMOS Power Amplifier for Wireless Communication at 2.45 GHz". 2012 International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies.
- [6] Wenyuan Li, Yulong Tan, "2.4GHz Power Amplifier with Adaptive Bias Circuit", Institute of RF- & OEICs Southeast University Nanjing, China, 2012 International Conference on Systems and Informatics (ICSAI 2012)
- [7] G. Monprasert, P. Suebsombut, T. Pongthavornkamol, S. Chalermwisutkul, "2.45 GHz GaN HEMT ClassAB RF Power Amplifier Design for Wireless Communication Systems", The Sirindhorn International Thai-German Graduate School of Engineering (TGGGS), King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, IEEE 2010
- [8] Yongbing Qian, Wenyuan Li, Zhigong Wang, "2.4-GHz 0.18- μ m CMOS Highly Linear Power Amplifier" Institute of RF- & OE-ICs, Southeast University, 210096 Nanjing, China, The 2010 International Conference on Advanced Technologies for Communications, 2010 IEEE
- [9] Cheng-Chi Yen Student Member, IEE and , Huey-Ru Chuang IEEE, "A 0.25 μ m 20-dBm 2.4-GHz CMOS Power Amplifier With an Integrated Diode Linearizer", MICROWAVE AND WIRELESS COMPONENTS LETTERS, VOL. 13, NO. 2, FEBRUARY 2003
- [10] Chia-Jun Chang, Po-Chih Wang, Chih-Yu Tsai, Chin-Lung Li, Chiao-Ling Chang, Han-Jung Shih, MengHsun Tsai, Wen-Shan Wang, Ka-Un Chan, and Ying-Hsi Lin, "A CMOS Transceiver with internal PA and Digital Pre-distortion For WLAN 802.11a/b/g/n Applications", 2010 IEEE Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits Symposium
- [11] Yi Zhao, John R. Long, and Marco Spirito, "A 60GHz-band 20dBm Power Amplifier with 20% Peak PAE", 2011 IEEE
- [12] Ville Saari, Pasi Juurakko, Jussi Ryyanen and Kari Halonen, "Integrated 2.4 GHz Class-E CMOS Power Amplifier" 2005 IEEE Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits Symposium

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SINGLE ELECTRON TRANSISTOR: APPLICATIONS & PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this paper is to review in brief the basic physics of nanoelectronic device single-electron transistor [SET] as well as prospective applications and problems in their applications. SET functioning based on the controllable transfer of single electrons between small conducting "islands". The device properties dominated by the quantum mechanical properties of matter and provide new characteristics coulomb oscillation, coulomb blockade that is helpful in a number of applications. SET is able to shear domain with silicon transistor in near future and enhance the device density. Recent research in SET gives new ideas which are going to revolutionize the random access memory and digital data storage technologies.

KEYWORDS

Nanoelectronics; Single-electron transistor; Coulomb blockade, Coulomb oscillation, Quantum dot

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Kastner, "The single electron transistor and artificial atoms", *Ann. Phys. (Leipzig)*, vol. 9, pp. 885-895, 2000.
- [2] S. Bednarek, B. Szafran, and J. Adamowski, "Solution of the Poisson Schrodinger problem for a single-electron transistor", *Phys. Rev. B*, Vol. 61, pp. 4461-4464, 2000.
- [3] Songphol Kanjanachuchai and Somsak Panyakeow, "Beyond CMOS: Single-Electron Transistors", IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology, Bangkok, Thailand, 2002.
- [4] Masumi Saitoh, Hidehiro Harata and Toshiro Hiramoto, "Room-Temperature Demonstration of Integrated Silicon Single-Electron Transistor Circuits for Current Switching and Analog Pattern Matching", IEEE International Electron Device Meeting, San Francisco, USA, 2004.
- [5] K. Matsumoto, M. Ishii, K. Segawa, Y. Oka B. J. Vartanian and J. S. Harris, "Room temperature operation of a single electron transistor made by the scanning tunneling microscope nano oxidation process for the TiOx/Ti system", *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 68 (1), pp. 34-36, 1996.
- [6] Ken Uchida, Jugli Kaga, Ryuji Ohba and Akira Toriumi, "Programmable Single-Electron Transistor Logic for Future Low-Power Intelligent LSI: Proposal and Room-Temperature Operation", *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, Vol. 50, No. 7, July 2003.
- [7] T.A. Fulton and G.D. Dolan, "Observation of single electron charging effect in small tunnelling junction", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 59, pp. 109-112, July 1987.
- [8] Lingjie Guo, Effendi Leobandung and Stephen Y. Chou, "A silicon Single-Electron transistor Memory operating at room temperature", *Science* Vol. 275, pp. 649-651, 1997.
- [19] A.N. Cleand, D. Estene, C. Urbina and M.H. Devoret, "An extremely Low noise Photodetector based on the single electron Transistor" , *Journal of Low Temperature Physics*, Vol. 93, Nos. 3/4, pp.767-772, 1993.
- [10] R. Knobel, C.s. Yung and A.N. clelanda, "Single -electron transistor as a radio frequency mixer", *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 81, No. 3, pp. 532-534, July 2002.

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DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF NINE STAGES CMOS BASED RING OSCILLATOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the design and performance analysis of a ring oscillator using CMOS 45nm technology process in Cadence virtuoso environment. The design of optimal Analog and Mixed Signal (AMS) very large scale integrated circuits (VLSI) is a challenging task for the integrated circuit(IC) designer. A Ring Oscillator is an active device which is made up of odd number of NOT gates and whose output oscillates between two voltage levels representing high and low. There are a number of challenges ahead while designing the CMOS Ring Oscillator which are delay, noise and glitches. CMOS is the technology of choice for many applications, CMOS oscillators with low power, phase noise and timing jitter are highly desired. In this paper, we have designed a CMOS ring oscillator with nine stages. Previously, the researchers were unable to reduce the phase noise in ring oscillators substantially with nine stages. We have successfully reduced the phase noise to -6.4kdBc/Hz at 2GHz center frequency of oscillation.

KEYWORDS

Analog and mixed signal (AMS), VLSI circuit, CMOS Ring oscillator (RO), integrated circuit (IC), phase noise, center frequency of oscillation

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bell and G. Borriello, "A single chip nMOS Ethernet controller," IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers, 1983, pp. 70–71.
- [2] B. Kim, D. Helman, and P. Gray, "A 30 MHz hybrid analog/digital clock recovery circuit in 2 um CMOS," IEEE J. Solid State Circuits, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 1385–1394, June 1990.
- [3] J. M. Rabaey, A. Chandrakasan, and B. Nikolic, Digital Integrated Circuits, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson/Prentice Hall, 2003.
- [4] N. Weste and D. Harris, CMOS VLSI Design. Boston, MA: Pearson/Addison-Wesley, 2005.
- [5] R. Bayruns, R. Johnston, D. Fraser, and S. C. Fang, "Delay analysis of Si nMOS Gbit/s logic circuits," IEEE J. Solid State Circuits, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 755–764, May 1984.
- [6] N. Hedenstierna and K. Jeppson, "CMOS circuit speed and buffer optimization," IEEE Trans. Computer Aided Design. Integrated Circuits Systems, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 270–281, Mar. 1987.
- [7] L. Bisdounis, S. Nikolaidis, and O. Loufopavlou, "Propagation delay and short circuit power dissipation modeling of the CMOS inverter," IEEE Trans. Circuits System International, Fundamental Theory Applications, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 259–270, Mar. 1998.
- [8] A. Kabbani, D. Al-Khalili, and A. Al-Khalili, "Technology portable analytical model for DSM CMOS inverter transition time estimation," IEEE Trans. Computer Aided Design Integrated Circuits Systems, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 1177–1187, Sep. 2003.
- [9] T. Weigandt, B. Kim, and P. Gray, "Analysis of timing jitter in CMOS ring oscillators," in Proc. IEEE Int. Symposium Circuits and Systems (ISCAS), 1994, pp. 27–30.
- [10] A. A. Abidi and R. G. Meyer, "Noise in relaxation oscillators," IEEE J. Solid State Circuits, vol. SC18, no. 6, pp. 794–802, Dec. 1983.
- [11] J. McNeill, "Jitter in ring oscillators," IEEE J. Solid State Circuits, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 870–879, Jun. 1997.
- [12] A. Hajimiri, S. Limotyrakis, and T. Lee, "Jitter and phase noise in ring oscillators," IEEE J. Solid State Circuits, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 790–804, Jun. 1999. International Journal of VLSI design & Communication Systems (VLSICS) Vol.3, No.3, June 2012 69
- [13] B. Leung, "A novel model on phase noise of ring oscillator based on last passage time," IEEE Trans. Circuits System International, Fundamental Theory Application, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 471–482, Mar. 2004.
- [14] Guang-Kaai Dehng, Ching-Yuan Yang, June-Ming Hsu, and Shen-Iuan Liu, "A 900 MHz 1 V CMOS Frequency Synthesizer," IEEE Journal of solid state circuits, Vol. 35, No. 8, pp. 1211–1214, 2000.
- [15] Andrea Bonfanti, Davide De Caro, Alfio Dario Grasso, Salvatore Pennisi, Carlo Samori, and Antonio G. M. Strollo, "A 2.5 GHz DDFS PLL with 1.8 MHz Bandwidth in 0.35 μm CMOS" IEEE Journal of Solid state circuits, Vol. 43, No. 6, pp. 1403–1413, 2008.

[16] Asad A. Abidi, Fellow, IEEE, "Phase Noise and Jitter in CMOS Ring Oscillators", IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, Vol. 41, No. 8, August 2006.

COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF XORXNOR FUNCTION BASED HIGH-SPEED CMOS FULL ADDER CIRCUITS FOR LOW VOLTAGE VLSI DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents comparative study of high-speed, low-power and low voltage full adder circuits. Our approach is based on XOR-XNOR design full adder circuits in a single unit. A low power and high performance 9T full adder cell using a design style called “XOR (3T)” is discussed. The designed circuit commands a high degree of regularity and symmetric higher density than the conventional CMOS design style as well as it lowers power consumption by using XOR (3T) logic circuits. Gate Diffusion Input (GDI) technique of low-power digital combinatorial circuit design is also described. This technique helps in reducing the power consumption and the area of digital circuits while maintaining low complexity of logic design. This paper analyses, evaluates and compares the performance of various adder circuits. Several simulations conducted using different voltage supplies, load capacitors and temperature variation demonstrate the superiority of the XOR (3T) based full adder designs in term of delay, power and power delay product (PDP) compared to the other full adder circuits. Simulation results illustrate the superiority of the designed adder circuits against the conventional CMOS, TG and Hybrid full adder circuits in terms of power, delay and power delay product (PDP). .

KEYWORDS

Hybrid full adder, XOR-XNOR circuit, High Speed, Low Power, Very Large Scale Integrated (VLSI) Circuits,

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<http://airccse.org/journal/vlsi/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] John P. Uyemura, (2002) Introduction to VLSI Circuits and Systems, John Wiley & Sons.
- [2] Sung-Mo Kang, Y. Leblebici, (2005) CMOS Digital Integrated Circuits: Analysis and Design, Tata McGraw Hill, New York, NY, USA.
- [3] N. Weste and D. Harris, (2005) CMOS VLSI Design, Pearson Wesley.
- [4] N. Zhuang and H. Wu, (1992) "A new design of the CMOS full adder," IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, Vol. 27, No. 5, pp. 840–844.
- [5] Y. Tsividis, (1996) Mixed Analog- Digital VLSI Devices and Technology, Singapore; McGraw Hill.
- [6] K.M. Chu and D. Puffrey, (1987) "A Comparison of CMOS Circuit Techniques Differential Cascode Voltage Switch Logic versus Conventional Logic," IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuit, Vol. SC 22, No. 4, pp. 528- 532.
- [7] A. P. Chandrakasan, S. Sheng and R. W. Bordersen, (1992) "Low-power CMOS digital design," IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, Vol. 27, No. 4, pp. 473- 484.
- [8] E. Abu-Sharma and M. Bayoumi, (1995) "A new cell for low power adders," in Proceeding of International Midwest Symposium Circuits System, pp. 1014-1017.
- [9] I. S. Abu-Khater, A. Bellaouar, and M.I. Elmasry, (1996) "Circuit techniques for CMOS low power high performance multipliers," IEEE Journal of Solid- State Circuits, Vol. 31, No. 10, pp. 1535-1546.
- [10] Uming Ko, Poras T. Balsara and Wai Lee, (1995) "Low-Power Design Techniques for HighPerformance CMOS adders," IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 327-333.
- [11] A. Bellaouar and M. I. Elmasry, (1995) Low-Power Digital VLSI Design: Circuits and Systems, Kluwer Academic.
- [12] A. Parameswar, H. Hara and T. Sakurai, (1994) "A high speed, low power, swing restored passtransistor logic based multiply and accumulate circuit for multimedia applications," in Proceedings of IEEE Custom Integrated Circuits Conference, San Diego, USA, pp. 278–281.
- [13] A. Parameswar, H. Hara and T. Sakurai, (1996) "A swing restored pass-transistor logic-based multiply and accumulate circuit for multimedia applications," IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, Vol. 31, No. 6, pp. 804–809.
- [14] K. Yano, Y. Sasaki, K. Rikino and K. Seki, (1996) "Top-down pass-transistor logic design," IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, Vol. 31, No. 6, pp. 792–803.
- [15] Reto Zimmermann and Wolfgang Fichtner, (1997) "Low-power Logic Styles: CMOS versus pass transistor logic," IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, Vol. 32, No. 7, pp. 1079-1090.
- [16] Ahmed M. Shams, and Magdy A. Bayoumi, (2000) "A Novel High- Performance CMOS 1-Bit FullAdder Cell," IEEE Transaction on Circuits and Systems. II, Vol. 47, No. 5, pp. 478–481.

- [17] Abdulkarim Al-Sheraidah, Yingtao Jiang, Yuke Wang and Edwin Sha, (2001) "A Novel Low Power Multiplexer-Based Full Adder," European Conference on Circuit Theory and Design, Espoo, Finland, pp. I329-I332.
- [18] D. Radhakrishnan, (2001) "Low-voltage low-power CMOS Full Adder," IEE Proceedings Circuit: Devices and Systems, Vol. 148, No. 1, pp. 19-24.
- [19] Fartash Vasefi and Z. Abid, (2005) "Low Power N-bit Adders and Multiplier using lowest number of Transistors 1-bit Adders," in Proceedings of IEEE Conference CCECE/CCGEI, 05 Saskatoon, pp. 1731-1734.
- [20] Sumeer Goel, Ashok Kumar, Magdy A. Bayoumi, (2006) "Design of Robust, Energy-Efficient Full Adders for Deep-Submicrometer Design Using Hybrid-CMOS Logic Style," IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems, Vol. 14, No. 12, pp. 1309-1321.
- [21] Ahmed M. Shams, Tarek K. Darwish, and Magdy A. Bayoumi, (2002) "Performance Analysis of Low-Power 1-Bit CMOS Full Adder Cells," IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems, Vol. 10, No. 1, pp. 20-29.
- [22] Mark Vesterbacka, (1999) "14-Transistor CMOS Full Adder with Full Voltage-Swing Nodes," in Proceedings of IEEE Workshop Signal Processing Systems, pp. 713-722.
- [23] R. Shalem, E. John and L. K. John, (1999) "Novel Low Power Energy Recovery Full Adder Cell," in Proceeding of 9th Great Lakes Symposium on VLSI (GLSVLSI'99), pp. 380-383.
- [24] Y. Jiang, A. Al-Sheraidah, Y. Wang, E. Shah, and J. Chung, (2004) "A Novel Multiplexer-Based Low Power Full Adder," IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems, Vol. 51, No. 7, pp. 345-348.
- [25] Hung Tien Bui, Yuke Wang and Yingtao Jiang, (2002) "Design and Analysis of Low-Power 10-Transistor Full Adders Using Novel XOR-XNOR Gates," IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Analog and Digital Signal Processing, Vol. 49, No. 1, pp. 25-30.
- [26] S. Wairya, Himanshu Pandey, R. K. Nagaria and S. Tiwari, (2010) "Ultra Low Voltage High Speed 1- Bit CMOS Adder," in Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Power, Control and Embedded System (ICPCES'10), India, pp. 1-6.
- [27] Chip-Hong Chang, Jiangmin Gu, Mingyan Zhang, (2005) "A Review of 0.18 μ m Full Adder Performances for Tree Structured Arithmetic Circuits," IEEE Transaction on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems, Vol. 13, No. 6, pp. 686-694.
- [28] Sumeer Goel, Mohammed A. Elgamel, Magdy A. Bayoumi, Yasser Hanafy, (2006) "Design Methodologies for High-Performance Noise-Tolerant XOR-XNOR Circuits," IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems- I, Vol. 53, No. 4, pp. 867-878.
- [29] Jin-Fa-Lin, Yin-Tsung Hwang, Ming-Hwa Sheu, and Cheng-Che Ho, (2007) "A Novel High-Speed and Energy Efficient 10-Transistor Full Adder Design," IEEE Transaction on Circuits and Systems I, Vol. 54, No. 5, pp. 1050-1059.
- [30] S. Veeramachaneni, M. B. Srinivas, (2008) "New Improved 1-Bit Full Adder Cells," CCECE /CCGEI, May 5-7, 2008, Niagara Falls, Ontario, Canada, pp. 735-738,.

- [31] Arkadiy Morgenshtein, Alexander Fish and Israel A. Wagner, (2002) "Gate-Diffusion Input (GDI): A Power Efficient Method for Digital Combinatorial Circuits," IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems, Vol. 10 No. 5, pp. 566 -581
- [32] Adarsh Kumar Agrawal, S. Wairya, R. K. Nagaria and S. Tiwari, (2009) "A New Mixed Gate Diffusion Input Full Adder Topology for High Speed Low Power Digital Circuits," World Applied Sciences Journal (WASJ) 7 (Special Issue of Computer & IT): pp. 138-144.
- [33] Mohammad Hossein Moaiyeri and Reza Faghieh Mirzaee, (2009) "Two New Low-Power and HighPerformance Full Adders," Journal of Computers, Vol. 4, No. 2, pp. 119-126.
- [34] MA Elgmal, S. Goel and M.A. Bayoumi, (2003) "Noise Tolerant Low Voltage XOR-XNOR for Fast Arithmetic," in Proceeding of IEEE Great Lakes Symposium on VLSI (GLSVLSI' 03), 2003, Wasting D.C., pp. 285-288.
- [35] Shiv Shankar Mishra, S. Wairya, R.K. Nagaria and S. Tiwari, (2009) "New Design Methodologies for High Speed Low Power XOR-XNOR Circuits," Journal of World Academy Science, Engineering and Technology (WASET), Vol. 55, No. 35, pp. 200-206.
- [36] S. Wairya, R. K. Nagaria and S. Tiwari, (2010) "A Novel CMOS Full Adder Topology for Low Voltage VLSI Applications," in Proceeding of International Conference on Emerging Trends in Signal Processing & VLSI Design (SPVL'10)', Hyderabad, India, pp. 1142-1146.
- [37] Shubhajit Roy Chowdhury, Aritra Banerjee, Aniruddha Roy and H. Saha, (2008) "A high Speed 8 Transistor Full Adder Design using Novel 3 Transistor XOR Gates," International Journal of Electronics, Circuits and Systems, WASET Fall, Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 217-223.
- [38] Mariano Aguirre-Hernandez and Monico Linares-Aranda, (2011) "CMOS Full Adders for EnergyEfficient Arithmetic Application," IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) System, Vol. 19, No. 4, pp. 718-721.
- [39] M. Hosseinghadiry, H. Mohammadi, M. Nadisenejani, (2009) "Two New Low Power High Performance Full Adders with Minimum Gates," International Journal of Electronics, Circuits and Systems, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 124-131.
- [40] Subodh Wairya, Rajendra Kumar Nagaria and Sudarshan Tiwari, (2011) "New Design Methodologies for High-Speed Low-Voltage 1 Bit CMOS Full Adder Circuits," Journal of Computer Technology and Application, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 190-198.
- [41] Subodh Wairya, Rajendra Kumar Nagaria and Sudarshan Tiwari, (2011) "New Design Methodologies for High Speed Mixed Mode Full Adder Circuits," International Journal of VLSI and Communication Systems, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 78-98.
- [42] Subodh Wairya, Garima Singh, Vishant, R. K. Nagaria and S. Tiwari (2011), "Design Analysis of XOR (4T) based Low Voltage CMOS Full Adder Cell," In Proceeding of IEEE International Conference on Current Trends In Technology (NUiCONE'11), Ahmedabad, India pp. 1-7.
- [43] Subodh Wairya, Rajendra Kumar Nagaria and Sudarshan Tiwari, (2012) "Performance Analysis of High Speed Hybrid CMOS Full Adder Circuits for Low Voltage VLSI Design," VLSI Design, Vol. 2012, Article ID 173079, 18 pages.